

Immortality

by
Albi Ndoni
(Extended)

My quest and reason for seeking an indefinite lifespan in this life.

1. I want a **PhD** in the following subjects:

- 1) **Mathematics**
- 2) **Physics**
- 3) **Computer Science**
- 4) **Medicine**
- 5) **Economics**
- 6) **Chemistry**
- 7) **Robotics**
- 8) **Literature**

2. I want to travel the **World, Solar System, Galaxy, Universe, Multiverse**, and beyond.

3. I want to win the **Nobel Prize** in each category, the **Fields Medal**, the **National Medal of Technology and Innovation**, and the **Pulitzer Prize**.

4. I want to become the **President** of the **United World Federation** in the **22nd -23rd century**.

5. I want to become a **trillionaire** and later a **(moneyless) quadrillionaire** (a person who has the wealth of a quadrillion dollars but no money which will become obsolete in the future).

6. The most important reason:

I want my Wikipedia page to be **googol, googolplex, googolduplex, googoltriplex, googolquadriplex, googolquintplex, googolsextiplex, googolseptiplex, googoloctiplex, googolnoniplex, googoldeciplex, googolcentiplex** of pages long...and more.

7. I want to become a **God** and master with my mind and will the entire known **Universe**.

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Albi Ndoni
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